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Analysis of Safety Culture in Maritime Companies

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Abstract

According to the International maritime organization, an organization with a safety culture gives appropriate priority to safety and realizes that safety has to be managed like other areas of business, “and the key to achieving a safety culture is in: a) Recognizing that accidents are preventable through following procedures and established best practices; b) Constantly thinking about safety; c) Seeking continuous improvement.

In recent years, attention to the behavioral and cultural aspects of safety management in large maritime organizations and corporations has increased significantly, as research has been conducted on major maritime accidents such as the Al-Salaam Boccaccio 98 In 2006 , which killed 1,101 people, and in 2002, the Le Joola which killed all 2,000 occupants, and the MT Sanchi which killed 32 crew members and caused pollution and More than 960,000 barrels of marine gas condensate contamination were detected, despite the use of all engineering, operational and severe protection factors in high-risk industries.

But in maritime operations, there is still great potential for accidents due to the nature of its activities. It is important to note that safety errors do not simply appear as individual errors and often lead to an inappropriate behavioral culture. Therefore, seeking to strengthen the safety culture in the maritime industry, which is one of the main organizational management issues and an expected value of an organization or company, is essential.

Keywords: safety culture, culture promotion strategy, industrial safety, organizational management.

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1. Introduction

Each country's labour is considered an essential part of the national capital and is one of the foundations of economic and social development, especially in developing countries. Undoubtedly, the prosperity and self-sufficiency of the economy and industry will not be possible without a healthy workforce. (Safety First: Technology, Labour, and Business in the Building of American - Mark Aldrich - Google Books, n.d.) Therefore, protecting the health of the crew and improving the work environment are essential. Statistics published by various countries and international organizations show that in large and small industrial centers, millions of people die every year due to work-related accidents or become disabled or sick, and this bitterness process continues.

The emergence of such problems has exacerbated the need to learn and adhere to the principles of occupational safety and health and has led individuals to seek accurate and scientific solutions to maintain the health of human resources.

Accordingly, industrial safety issues, occupational safety systems, and various safety theories, such as domino theory, multi-reason theory, etc., were formed. Occupational safety and health departments have solved occupational health and safety problems in industrial societies and sought to reduce accidents; therefore, establishing safety departments in maritime industrial companies seems vital, too (Chan & Chan, 2011).

Have you ever wondered what causes accidents and how to mitigate their occurrence? Accidents are caused by unsafe behavior or conditions that often result from hazardous situations and reflect the company's safety culture. While an institution or company's safety culture is at a suitable level, people's behaviors are safer, resulting in fewer accidents; consequently, the damage is significantly less. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the prevailing safety culture, which can be examined and implemented in various aspects.

Usually, following the shock of an accident, the management of industrial units and technological systems decide to trace the root causes. If this assessment is done correctly, the cause of the accident will remain the same in the design and other cases. Combined with special operating conditions, hardware failures, human error, and organizational defects can cause other accidents.

Some of the characteristics of safety culture that are derived from the general aspects of culture are as follows:

- Safety culture is learnable; therefore, it can be said that one of the main reasons for the inadequacy of safety culture is the low level of awareness of people. Accordingly, one of the ways to improve it is to raise awareness through various training.
- Safety culture includes rules that can be analyzed scientifically. Safety culture is structural and can be divided into various aspects; by analyzing the weaknesses and strengths in each element, it is possible to develop optimal strategies to promote safety culture.
- Safety culture is dynamic, evolving, and changeable, and problematic aspects of safety culture can be changed over time.

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- Safety culture is a tool for expressing people's creativity in the safety field and its promotion, and creating a participatory platform is a practical step in promoting a safety culture. Also, Culture is social security; in other words, cultural habits have social roots, and the institution's employees are partners. Norms or behavior patterns are driven by group or community practices.
- Safety culture adapts to people's behavior; change and its transformation are always accompanied by adaptation. These features can be called the main assumptions of the safety culture promotion process; in other words, the process of promoting safety culture is based on the fundamental premise that culture is not a fixed and unchangeable thing, and it can be done by scientific analysis of aspects. In the context of public participation, people gradually and, in the long run, changed and continuously improved using motivational mechanisms and educational programs (Schulman, 2020).

2. Methodology

This cross-sectional study reviewed articles about safety culture in the maritime industry as a critical point of view in marine transport. The critical literature review was conducted in 5 main steps: (i) online database search based on keywords (Scopus and Web of Science), (ii) first refinement based on selection criteria including title, abstract, and keywords of that paper, (iii) further refinement based on unique characteristics such as publishing year, language, type of document, type of access, region and country, etc., (iv) third refinement on abstract screening to consider focusing on the main topic and being related with the main subject, and (v) the last step is full-text review.

3. Attitudes About Safety Issues and HSE

3.1. The Traditional Attitude of Safety

One of the reasons for the failure of the traditional method of safety management in industrial facilities can be considered the weakness of the authorities' view of safety. One of the components of the conventional view of safety is the assumption of safety by managers. The traditional perspective is to ignore the impact of human, organizational, and cultural factors on safety. The conventional view considers safety based on solid design and reliable operation of safety equipment. The solution to the problem of human error is to cut off humans (operators) from control. Still, it is impossible in the maritime industry and maritime services as an operator. On the other hand, the inability of automatic systems to deal with unforeseen emergencies has proven this theory incorrect (Griffiths, 2007).

Today, it has become clear that creativity and finding new ways to deal with accidents in unforeseen circumstances in design is only possible in the human imagination, which can be the same as the ship's pilotage or ships manager, etc. in the marine industry, and it's not possible to relay it to machinery.

The traditional approach to safety is responsive; managers do not think about troubleshooting until the accident occurs. The cost-effectiveness of safety promotion makes it challenging to

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pay attention to security in situations where the system's operating characteristics are optimal, and no abnormalities have occurred.

Safety promotion attracts managers' attention when the occurrences of unusual events and, ultimately, events have adverse economic or social effects. In the traditional view, paying attention to and taking care of safety issues is the responsibility of a particular group or unit placed in the set (individual or occupational health and safety unit), and other departments are only concerned with increasing production indicators. Demonstrating compliance with standards and safety rules and regulations by managers is considered a successful safety performance time; the new approach requires more than compliance with safety standards and regulations (Henning et al., 2009).

3.2. New Prospective of Safety

In recent years, errata concepts have changed in many ways, especially since the middle of the twentieth century. An increase in population has led to a human need for production and, as a result, a slight increase in the size of industrial facilities and tools. On the other hand, the growth of social welfare and awareness of the harmful effects of pollutants, waste, and the end consequences of industrial accidents have put increasing pressure on managers. The role of human and organizational factors is becoming increasingly apparent. Improper use of industrial machinery and hardware made with advanced technology can lead to accidents. On the other hand, there are machines that, despite being old or weak in design, are used without incident due to the vigilance of management and personnel and awareness of their weaknesses or the existence of a strong safety culture (Griffiths, 2007).

Attention to safety culture has a unique role in the modern management attitude toward safety. Providing motivation, the spirit of ownership, responsibility, and accountability in individuals, and practical commitment of managers to the principle of safety priority over other aspects such as production, are among features of an organization with a safety culture, in companies with this type of attitude, the roots of small events that because accidents are identified and ineffective. The spirit of criticism and questioning prevails among the staff, and an environment far from being blamed for human error has been provided (Griffiths, 2007).

Behavior as a manager, operator, or maintenance specialist in an industrial environment, such as a ship or vessel that has a potentially hazardous environment and requires compliance with individual discipline and strict work regulations, cannot be much different from his social behavior in other situations, such as driving. Therefore, it is essential to study the national culture and determine the cases of incompatibility with the safety culture, especially in extensive industrial facilities. Among the new concepts of safety, attention to the category of organizational and cultural elements surrounding the personnel of industrial facilities. Unlike traditional methods, human error analysis has been done mainly by considering organizational and cultural formative factors in recent years. In this model, the interaction of organizational structure, communication mechanisms, instructions, personal tendencies of managers, corporate culture, and the impact of managers on the workplace in the occurrence of human

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errors are considered. Attention to safety issues is a mindset of all personnel and the responsibility of one department (Henning et al., 2009).

3.3. Organizational and Safety Culture

According to the existing definitions, organizational culture is a set of shared values, beliefs, and behavioral patterns between members of an institution or company that ultimately introduces the personality and procedure of that company. In other words, the behavior and attitudes of company members are a function of the culture that governs it. This definition aims to identify a similar and dependent concept called safety culture.

The term safety culture became popular after the 1986 Chernobyl accident. The accident was caused by a weak safety culture and errors and violations that disrupted operational processes and ultimately caused a major global catastrophe. From a set of definitions presented in this chapter, it appears that safety culture is part of the overall culture governing an organization or company that influences and directs personnel's behaviors and attitudes toward safety (Sexton et al., 2006).

The UKSNI (United Kingdom Safety of Nuclear Installations) defines safety culture as follows: Safety culture is the product of the values, tendencies, perceptions, competencies, and patterns of individual and personnel's behavior, the extent to which employees adhere to the style and manner of safety management. It determines the organization's health (Hollnagel, 2014).

Galden Mand's definition of safety culture is:

Aspects of organizational culture that affect attitudes and behaviors lead to reduced or increased risks (Sklet, 2006).

Traces of defects in the safety culture of the marine industry can also be found in other significant accidents, such as Mt. Sanchi.

Organizational culture means universal values and understanding among an organization's people, which is motivated by informal notions following specific geographical, ethnic, historical, and social development characteristics and is even referred to as the unwritten law of the organization. One issue in any company's culture is people's attitude towards safety, which is called safety culture. Safety culture is the general definition of a society whose members share common organizational values. Safety culture talks about legal safety issues in a company and is deeply about managing and monitoring systems, but not limited to them (Hollnagel, 2014).

"Safety is a culture and can't be created just by Safety First." (Safety Management and Safety Culture, n.d.)

- Safety culture is the same part of a group's thoughts in a company at any level.
- Safety culture is a part that affects the safe behavior of employees.
- Safety culture is reflected in the likelihood of an immune system and immune function.
- Safety culture in organizational tendencies is learning from mistakes and consequences of accidents and expanding these findings in the organization.
- Safety culture is relatively tolerant of change.

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3.4. The importance of safety culture in the maritime industry

In the maritime industry, it is more important to follow safety regulations than to perform all activities. Recognizing, classifying, preventing, and controlling accidents before any other action creates and promotes a safety culture. Safe work is a human and cultural attitude, which means that a company's safety culture expands when the desired mood of personnel needs to observe safety principles towards the ideal. (Safety Management and Safety Culture, n.d.) Weak industrial safety culture in marine companies as a serious and vital industrial company causes a lot of financial and human costs and damages and can have vast, critical. Long-term impacts on the environment, such as accidents, can be named the most important in recent years: (Casualties, n.d.)

- 1) The ship Donya Pass with 4386 casualties in 1987 in the Sea of Tubas, Philippines.
- 2) The ship Le Joola was damaged by the death of 2,000 passengers in 2002 off the coast of Gambia.
- 3) The ship Al-Salaam Boccaccio 98 with 1101 passenger casualties in 2006 in the Red Sea.
- 4) The ship Impress Atlantic with pollution 2,000,000 barrels of oil in 1979 in the Caribbean Sea.
- 5) The ship Costello Dabloor contaminated 1,800,000 barrels of oil in 1983 in the South African Sea.
- 6) The ship Abt Summer with 1,900,000 barrels of oil pollution in 1991 off the coast of Angola.

Although the words culture and environmental effects are used interchangeably in many cases, these two terms have entirely different meanings.

Working conditions at first seem apparent, but there needs to be a clear definition of workplace conditions. It may be argued that the working environment conditions how employees react and understand rules set in an institution, the executive instructions, or even the behavior of each department head. The definitions given for a safe environment have many semantic variations. Safety in environmental conditions is a psychological manifestation often interpreted as a perception of safety conditions at certain times. A safe environment is related to intangible issues such as environmental factors.

A safe environment is a physical manifestation and a quick approach to safety culture and is relatively unstable to change.

4. Discussion

Maritime activities are potentially hazardous operations by nature, then establishing Strategies for the Successful Implementation of Safety Culture are as follows: (Vecchio-Sadus & Griffiths, 2004).

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4.1. Preparing and Distributing Safety Instructions

Providing complete and basic guidelines and standards is a vital part of a safety system in an industry or company. The instructions specify how a critical task should be performed regarding safety and efficiency; a supervisor or operator uses instructions. Acknowledges the correctness of the work done. The instructions make the training program easier and make it easier to identify methods to improve operations (Vecchio-Sadus & Griffiths, 2004).

4.2. Training of Safety Principles and Regulations

The role of occupational safety and health education in raising employees' safety knowledge, awareness of physical and mental health, understanding disease symptoms and how to deal with them, prevention of accidents, and creating and promoting a safety culture is essential and unavoidable. Training can enable a person to engage themselves promptly, if necessary, by following safety guidelines. Both short-term and long-term training to address and identify risks and dangers in the working atmosphere can help maritime companies mitigate accidents and incidents and promote organizational safety culture (Sorensen, 2002).

4.3. Establishing the HSE Department

The HSE department aims to monitor the overall health system in health, safety, and environmental factors to ensure that work is being done correctly and that injuries and diseases are being referred to in human resources and hardware resources such as tools and vessels are declining. The general activities of this department are:

Safety activities include identifying potential and actual safety and personal and environmental health problems, proposing programs, plans and activities to improve safety, such as emergency maneuvers, and increasing monitoring of employee awareness in the safety and health field. It also receives comments and suggestions from managers, safety experts, and union officials. It includes periodical meetings with at least one department representative presenting specific activities, programs, and problems related to their department; in this regard, those representatives must contact all department personnel and groups to ensure that all cases are considered (Wiegmann et al., 2009).

4.4. Personal Protective Equipment

Ergonomically, a suitable personal protective device is a device that does not relieve a person's ability and efficiency while reducing or eliminating hazards and harmful factors in the workplace. Personal protective equipment or devices designed and manufactured to protect different parts of a person's body, from hair to the soles of the feet, against a variety of potential hazards in the workplace. Using these tools to control staff exposure to hazards may seem like a simple and appropriate solution to employers; ignoring the many factors in a prevention program can be very harmful and dangerous (Vecchio-Sadus & Griffiths, 2004).

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4.6. Establishing Department's Safety Monitoring Systems

Monitoring performance, as seen at all levels of management, is essential for career advancement. The administration must insist that safety monitoring be the first issue to be discussed in the report of each operational department, whether it is the company's annual report or a single monthly report from that company. The Safety Monitoring System seeks to determine how well each person or unit of the company is on the target path and the organization's standard that has already been set or how much it deviates (which is essentially preparing checklists). It is achievable, as well as its strengths and weaknesses, and offers solutions and suggestions to strengthen it further (Sorensen, 2002).

4.7. Information Base, Safety Warnings, and Incident Management Process

Since human beings have always needed to be reminded and repeated to learn and acquire operational problems and issues, therefore, to maintain and improve the safety culture level, in addition to training and implementing management policies, a database should be formed of daily topics, principles, regulations, safety warnings and incident analysis for all personnel working in an organization or company. For this purpose, in the internal automation of the company, circulars, brochures, and safety instructions have to be sent alternately to different departments, units, and branches (Hollnagel, 2014).

4.8. Visual Management Through Signs and Posters

Another tool used to improve safety and health is the use of signs and the distribution of posters with the subject of HSE. Signs and posters neither safeguard employees nor make them work safely. But as the safety culture in an organization grows, signs and posters can remind employees of the importance of safety in the workplace. Employees can also be reminded that management is concerned about employee safety (Sorensen, 2002).

4.9. Promoting Safe Methods in Maintenance and Repair System

Each industrial department's basis and axis of activity are its equipment and machinery, and any disruption in the company's machinery performance means damage and cessation in the output.

Therefore, activities led to the definition of PM and CM activities implementation projects, which despite the cultural context of technical and safety personnel, has led to optimal performance in terms of continuous improvement of maritime activities and floating services (Wiegmann et al., 2009).

4.10. Senior Management's Attention to Safety Procedures

the safety culture will be strengthened while the management system supports safety issues and the process of paying attention to safety and HSE; otherwise, it will be weakened.

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Without senior managerial support, the escape from observing safety principles will increase. In such cases, costly external control systems or external monitoring units will be deployed instead of internal control.

Although, it is only possible to implement organizational culture with the will of the company's top management, even if the authorities try to implement it. Senior management of a company or institution with support in the field of planning and reviewing all financial matters, advertising, organizing meetings, attending employee meetings, encouraging, and rewarding (identifying individuals or units with positive performance through evaluation Monthly or HSE competitions and with the cooperation of other company agents can help create, promote and sustain a culture (Sorensen, 2002).

5. Conclusion

About 80% of accidents are rooted in human factors and go back to human error. (Wiegmann et al., 2009) Therefore, to achieve a safe and healthy environment, preserve human resources, and, as a result, reach a dynamic industry that is a critical factor in sustainable development, it is necessary to deal with quasi-accidents and eliminate their root causes radically. A significant factor that can help us in this way is safety culture.

Examination of accidents shows that most of them are rooted in human factors and safety culture at different levels of personnel; (Schulman, 2020). This is where the role of safety culture becomes apparent. A conclusion can be reached: to make the workplace safer and reduce the number of accidents and costs. Their consequences need to pay more attention to safety culture so we can deal with the events in a radical and principled way.

Safety culture, which is part of organizational culture, must change to create a safe and healthy environment and promote safe behavior and a kind of attitude to safety at a company's level. Strong safety culture in that institution can be a determining factor in reducing human resources accidents in the company. Organizational factors, as well as the position of the safety sector in terms of structure, play a significant role in governing a solid safety culture, which results in reduced accidents and a safe environment for personnel.

Measures recommended to institutionalize safety culture in the organization include:

1. Considering the type of people's attitude towards work safety in selecting and appointing them as managers and supervisors in addition to their expertise and commitment to production.
2. Develop, implement, and maintain safety regulations, HSE, and its comprehensive support by senior management.
3. Continuous review of updated safety and HSE guidelines and regulations following current conditions.
4. Active participation of managers and supervisors in periodic visits of vessels and related departments.
5. Using the company's welfare facilities, etc., to encourage people who are role models to observe the rules and principles of occupational safety and duty.

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6. Using the latest scientific achievements of the world and following the example of leading companies in the field of marine safety activities to improve the quality of work safety guidelines.
7. Establish a system of safety suggestions.
8. Establishment of a safety committee of branches and departments other than the central core to identify the existing risks at that branch level.
9. Introducing the top safety personnel of that quasi-event for technical analysis of problems and accidents, quasi-accidents, reviewing safety instructions, and preparing safety reports.
10. Organizing safety morning meetings in smaller workshops, followed by studying unsafe cases of those workshops.
11. Introducing the best people and role models in observing safety principles and regulations during celebrations and domestic publications.
12. Remind and warn the safety points of the work before the personnel start working by the supervisors.
13. Definition of the person in charge of researching to solve work safety problems by the company's senior management.
14. Develop a company safety charter using local, national, and international standard rules.

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